

COMPETENCIES OF K TO 12 TEACHERS AND ITS RELATION TO JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOLS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS: BASIS FOR TRAINING PLANS

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Competencies of K to 12 Teachers and Its Relation to Junior High Schools' Academic Performance in Mathematics: Basis for Training Plans

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to determine the competencies of K–12 mathematics teachers and their relationship to junior high school students' academic performance in mathematics. It uses a descriptive type of research design. The study utilized a survey questionnaire and document analysis to collect data from mathematics teachers and their students in five public schools. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-tests, and correlation analysis. The findings of the study revealed that the competency level of mathematics teachers in terms of dedication to teaching, knowledge of the subject matter, classroom organization and management, instructional organization and implementation, and profile characteristics of teachers like civil status and highest training attended significantly affected the mathematics performance of students. Additionally, civil status significantly impacted teachers' competency level. There was no significant difference in teachers' IPCRF performance when grouped according to their profile characteristics. Moreover, there was no significant relationship between teachers' IPCRF ratings and students' mathematics performance. Based on the results, the study suggests a training plan for K–12 mathematics teachers, which includes identifying the competencies that need improvement, providing in-service training, and offering technical assistance to improve teaching competence and instructional implementation. Furthermore, parents can utilize the findings to identify their children's weaknesses and provide them with motivation to improve their academic performance.

Keywords: *competencies of k to 12 teachers, IPCRF rating, mathematics performance, training plan*

Introduction

The K to 12 programs in the Philippines added two more years to the basic education curriculum to provide globally competitive skills and knowledge. However, implementing the program and facilitating effective learning has been challenging for teachers. Common problems related to K to 12 teachers' competencies and their impact on junior high school academic performance in mathematics include insufficient training, content knowledge, classroom management, and assessment competencies. Improving teacher competencies is crucial in ensuring students' success in the K to 12 programs. A study by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) argues that effective teaching largely depends on the teacher's knowledge of mathematics content and pedagogy, as well as their ability to implement effective instructional strategies. Therefore, it is essential to examine the competencies of K to 12 mathematics teachers to provide a basis for developing a training plan that was supported the enhancement of teachers' teaching skills in mathematics. This study focused on the competencies of K to 12 mathematics teachers and their relation to junior high schools' academic performance in mathematics. Specifically, the study was investigated the different competencies of K to 12 mathematics teachers and determine their relationship with the academic performance of students in junior high school mathematics. Facts and observations shown that students lack the mastery in mathematics competencies as shown in the National Achievement Test 2017 -2018 results Manjuyod District 1 and 2 was 29.91 and Mabinay National High School, District of Mabinay 3 have an average MPS of 49.8. Moreover, during quarterly assessment for the school year 2022-2023 Grade 7 Mathematics in Manjuyod District 1 and 2 and Mabinay District 3 obtained an average MPS 84 which was interpreted as satisfactory.

Thus, this study was conducted to determine if there is significant relationship between the competencies of a K to 12 teachers and the Junior High School's academic performance in Mathematics of Manjuyod District and Mabinay District 3. The result of this study can be a great help of the education program supervisor, coordinators and school administration in the formulation of training plans to enhance teacher competence and acquire effective teaching strategies to help improve the academic performance of the students.

Methodology

This study used the descriptive correlational design and inferential statistics to determine if there was a relationship between the competencies of a K to 12 teacher and the academic performance in Mathematics of the Junior high school students of the Department of Education - Division of Negros Oriental, Manjuyod District and Mabinay National High School – Mabinay District 3. The researcher chose to conduct this study based on the criteria such as: (a) the location of the study was where the most students as to population in the whole district (b) the location of the study had the greatest number of teachers (c) some the challenged students and teachers were in the identified location of the study due to its population. This study used a self-made questionnaire method in gathering of data.

The instrument used in this study was composed of 2 sets. First set was for teachers and the other set was for the students since the students were also assessed the competency level of their teachers. Teacher's questionnaire composed of demographic profile and competency level, however, student's questionnaire focused only the competency level of the teachers. In addition to, the IPCRF rating

of the teachers from SY 2019 – 2022 and grades of the students SY 2022 -2023 were also gathered as secondary data to be used as basis to determine the performance of the teachers and academic performance of the students.

In order to determine the mathematics performance of the students in Mathematics in four rating periods, mean and standard deviation were used.

Results and Discussion

Profile Characteristics of Mathematics Teachers

It showed that the majority of the mathematics teachers were 25 to 35 years old, comprising 46% of the total population. In terms of civil status and sex, 81% were married and female, and 19% were single and male. For the number of years in service as math teachers, the majority of them have 11 to 15 years in service. In terms of position, highest educational attainment, and highest training attended, most of the teachers were Teacher III, who has earned master’s units and has attended district-level training only.

Table 1. Profile characteristics of mathematics teachers

<i>Profile Of The Students</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age	Under 25	2	8
	25-30	6	23
	31-35	6	23
	36-40	4	15
	41-45	3	11
	46-50	2	8
	51-55	1	4
	Over 55	2	8
Civil Status	Single	5	19
	Married	21	81
	Total	26	100
Sex	Male	5	19
	Female	21	81
	Total	26	100
Years of Teaching as Math Teacher	5 years and below	0	0
	6-10 years	7	27
	11-15 years	11	42
	16-20 years	5	19
	21 and above	3	12
	Total	26	100
Position	Teacher 1	11	42
	Teacher 2	1	4
	Teacher 3	13	50
	Master Teacher	1	4
	Total	26	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor’s Degree	3	12
	Earned Masters Units	18	69
	Master’s Degree	4	15
	Earned Doctorate Units	1	4
	Doctorate Degree Holder	0	0
Total	26	100	
Highest Trainings Attended	District	16	62
	Division	1	4
	Regional	8	31
	National	1	4
Total	26	100	

Competency Level of Mathematics Teachers as Assessed by Themselves and their Students

The competency level of mathematics teachers as assessed by themselves and their students was found very satisfactory. Teachers were highly competent as mathematics instructors; they knew the learning competencies very well, and they knew how to achieve their target outcomes and had knowledge of managing their mathematics lessons daily. It implies that students assessed their teacher as knowledgeable in the contents and concepts they teach in mathematics, and they knew how to relate, integrate, and apply their lessons to help students better learn skills in mathematics. According to Umbac (2016) Teachers’ competency level based on NCBTS and its relation to teachers’ and pupils’ performance revealed that teachers’ competency is significantly related to their performance in the performance evaluation system. In general, it was concluded that the higher the competency of teachers, the better is their job performance. Meanwhile competence directly affects performance, and determine the quality of work (Herppich et al., 2018).

Table 2.1. *Competency level of mathematics teachers as assessed by themselves*

Indicators	Mean	Sd	Interpretation
a. dedication to teaching	3.985	0.565	Very Satisfactory
b. knowledge of subject matter	4.108	0.540	Very Satisfactory
c. classroom organization and management	4.246	0.481	Very Satisfactory
d. instructional organization	4.169	0.444	Very Satisfactory
e. instructional implementation	4.177	0.567	Very Satisfactory

Table 2.2. *Competency level of mathematics teachers as assessed by their students*

Indicators	Mean	Sd	Interpretation
a. dedication to teaching	4.392	0.760	Very Satisfactory
b. knowledge of subject matter	4.360	0.813	Very Satisfactory
c. classroom organization and management	4.358	0.853	Very Satisfactory
d. instructional organization	4.395	0.395	Very Satisfactory
e. instructional implementation	4.399	0.399	Very Satisfactory

Level of Teachers' IPCRF Performance

The table shows that the level of teachers' IPCRF rating for three consecutive years from SY 2019 - 2022 were all very satisfactory. It implies that the teachers' performance were very satisfactory in their IPCRF rating in three consecutive years from SY 2019-2022. It can be deduced from the finding that majority of the teachers exhibits a very satisfactory performance. According to Sabado (2014) on DepEd Teachers having very satisfactory performance rating that it is expected performance of the proficient teachers who went through a lot of trainings and workshops. Affirmatively, in the Department of Education, having a high job performance yields satisfactory to outstanding ratings. This means that teachers perform well with their work and display effectiveness, efficiency, and timeliness in doing their duties most especially related to the different Key Result Areas: content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and plus factors. Teacher performance is indeed complex and involves various factors. Nemeth, 2017 stated that many factors affect individual performance, including that of teachers, such as ability, motivation, and support received, existence of the work done, and their relationship with the organization. Varied efforts have been made in improving teacher performance. They include improving teacher professionalism through training, seminars, courses or formal higher education, as well as coaching and development to support effective learning.

Table 3. *Level of teachers' IPCRF performance*

Indicators	Mean	Sd	Interpretation
IPCRF 2020-2021	4.077	.272	Very Satisfactory
IPCRF 2021-2022	4.308	.471	Very Satisfactory
IPCRF 2022-2023	4.346	.485	Very Satisfactory

Level of Academic Performance in Mathematics of Students

The level of academic performance of students in Mathematics in the first grading period to third grading period and when taken as a whole was found as satisfactory while very satisfactory during 4th grading period. It implies that students performed better in their Mathematics subject during fourth grading period expecting to cover up other periods they less performed with. Additionally, it is during 4th grading period they performed at their best knowing that it was their only chance to help their other grades in other grading periods to increase. Narad and Abdullah (2016) stated that academic performance is the knowledge gained which assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time and these goals are measured by using continuous assessment or examinations result. Scand (2013) mentioned that one way to improve students' achievement is to make possible the provision of effective teachers.

Table 4. *Level of mathematics performance in mathematics of students*

Indicators	Mean	Sd	Interpretation
First Grading	82.134	5.882	Satisfactory
Second Grading	83.901	4.830	Satisfactory
Third Grading	84.398	5.132	Satisfactory
Fourth Grading	85.953	4.883	Very Satisfactory
As a whole Performance in Mathematics	84.232	4.312	Satisfactory

Difference between the Level of competency of Mathematics teachers as assessed by themselves and their students when grouped by Teachers' Profile Characteristics

As assessed by both teachers and students it found that there was a significant difference in terms of the level of competency of Mathematics Teachers when grouped by civil status. It implies that single Mathematics teachers displays more interest in teaching Mathematics subject than married ones, they were able to perform the task and could accomplish most of the time in Mathematics subject they teach. On the other hand, age, sex, years in teaching, position, highest educational attainment, and highest training attended was found to have no significant difference. It implies that teachers were competent in teaching Mathematics regardless of teacher's

age, sex, and length of stay in the service as Math teacher, position, highest educational attainment and highest trainings attended. A study conducted by Griller and his colleagues (2019) found that teachers' age, sex, and years of experience did not have a significant impact on their effectiveness in teaching mathematics. Similarly, a study conducted by Zhang and colleagues (2018) found that teachers' educational background and training did not have a significant impact on their performance in teaching mathematics.

Table 5. *Difference between the Level of competency of Mathematics teachers as assessed by themselves and their students when grouped according to teachers' Profile*

Profile of Teachers		Level of Competency of Mathematics Teachers	
		As assessed by Teachers	As assessed by Students
Age	F/t Value	1.686	5.622
	p-value	0.975	0.584
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
Civil Status	F/t Value	0.871	0.922
	p-value	0.027	0.10
	Interpretation	Significant	Significant
	Decision	Reject Ho	Reject Ho
Sex	F/t Value	0.272	0.344
	p-value	0.602	0.557
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
Years in Teaching	F/t Value	2.016	2.291
	p-value	0.569	0.514
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
Position	F/t Value	2.323	1.967
	p-value	0.508	0.579
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
Highest Educational Attainment	F/t Value	0.720	0.433
	p-value	0.869	0.933
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
Highest Training Attended	F/t Value	0.683	3.560
	p-value	0.711	0.169
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho

Difference between the Mathematics performance of students when grouped according to their Teachers' Profile

Based on the result, it shows that there was a significant difference between the highest training attended and the mathematics performance of students. This implies that attending additional training in mathematics can improve a teacher's ability to teach mathematics to students. This finding suggests that teachers who have undergone specialized training in mathematics will perform better in teaching mathematics to students. Therefore, providing teachers with regular professional development opportunities related to mathematics can be beneficial. Research has consistently demonstrated that specialized training in mathematics can significantly improve teacher effectiveness in teaching mathematics (Chin, 2017; Li, Zhu, & Yang, 2019). Providing teachers with regular professional development opportunities related to mathematics can be beneficial for improving their ability to teach mathematics to students.

Table 6. *Difference between the Mathematics Performance of Students when grouped according to their teachers' Profile*

Profile of Teachers		Mathematics Performance of Students
Age	p-value	0.269
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Civil Status	p-value	0.241
	Interpretation	Significant
	Decision	Reject Ho
Sex	p-value	0.079
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Years in Teaching		

Position	p-value	0.562
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Highest Educational Attainment	p-value	0.121
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Highest Training Attended	p-value	0.641
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
	p-value	0.036
	Interpretation	Significant
	Decision	Reject Ho

Additionally, there is significant difference between civil status and the mathematics performance of the students. This implies that the marital status of a teacher may influence their ability to teach mathematics. One study found that teachers who were married had better time management skills, which could positively affect their ability to teach mathematics (Nemeth & Ryan, 2014).

However, age, sex number of years in teaching, position, and highest educational attainment did not affect the performance of the students. Both male and female, novice and veteran teachers can be equally effective in teaching mathematics to students. The literature suggests that years of teaching do not significantly affect a teacher’s ability to teach mathematics (Bacchieri & Urbano, 2015; Boles & Troen, 2016) and age should not be a factor when selecting teachers for teaching mathematics.

Difference between the IPCRF performance of teachers’ when grouped according to their Profile

The profile of teachers was analyzed in relation to their IPCRF rating. The age, civil status, sex, years in teaching, position, highest educational attainment, and highest training attended were found to have no significant difference in their IPCRF rating.

The study suggests that while the examined factors, including age, civil status, sex, years in teaching, position, highest educational attainment, and highest training attended are not significant in teacher performance, educational institutions should consider other factors that can contribute to teacher performance. Educational institutions can further investigate which factors could best measure teachers' performance and use them to develop a comprehensive teacher assessment program (Barrett & O’Connell, 2019).

Table 7. *Difference between the IPCRF performance of teachers’ when grouped according to their Profile*

Profile of Teachers		Teachers’ IPCRF Rating
Age	p-value	0.912
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Civil Status	p-value	0.775
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Sex	p-value	0.278
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Years in Teaching	p-value	0.731
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Position	p-value	0.699
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Highest Educational Attainment	p-value	0.142
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho
Highest Training Attended	p-value	0.160
	Interpretation	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho

Relationship between the level of competencies of Mathematics Teachers as Assessed by Themselves and their Students and their Mathematics Performance

The teachers assessed their competencies in terms of Instructional organization was found to have significant relationship to their performance in Mathematics. It implies that teacher's organization during their instruction was found to increase students Mathematics performance. Meaning, the more organized was the teacher the better students perform academically in Mathematics. On the contrary, dedication to teaching, knowledge of the subject matter, classroom organization and management and instructional implementation has nothing to do with their performance in mathematics since it was found that there was no correlation. It implies that students can learn concepts in Math regardless of how their teacher implements their leaning competencies during instruction, how teachers organized and manage their classroom, their knowledge on the subject matter, and their dedication in teaching.

The students assessed their teachers' teaching competencies in terms of dedication in teaching, knowledge of the subject matter, classroom organization and management, instructional organization and instructional implementation was found to have significant relationship to their performance in Mathematics. It implies that students perform better in their Mathematics subject of their teacher was organized during instruction and in presenting their lesson to them including the activities in both written and performance task. Moreover, students also performed academically when their teacher was dedicated in teaching them with their lessons. In addition, if their teacher was knowledgeable in their subject matter, knows how to manage their class and organized their classroom and skilled enough in implementation of the learning competencies and other important or basic skills in Mathematics students were more likely to gain more interest in learning.

The finest teachers display enthusiasm and excitement for the subjects they teach. More than just generating excitement, they provide a road map for students to reach the goals set before them. The best teachers are proficient in the technical competencies of teaching: instructional delivery, formative assessment, and classroom management. Equally significant, they are fluent in a multilayered set of social skills that students recognize and respond to, which leads to greater learning (Attakorn, Tayut, Pissihawat & Kanakorn, 2014).

Table 8. Relationship between the Level of Competencies of Mathematics Teachers as assessed by Teachers and Students and their Academic Performance

Competency Level of Mathematics Teachers		Academic Performance in Mathematics	
		As Assessed by Teachers	As Assessed by Students
dedication to teaching	Correlation Coefficient	0.060	0.222
	p-value	0.772	0.000
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Significant
knowledge of subject matter	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Reject Ho
	Correlation Coefficient	0.077	0.245
	p-value	0.709	0.000
classroom organization and management	Interpretation	Not Significant	Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Reject Ho
	Correlation Coefficient	0.252	0.263
instructional organization	p-value	0.214	0.000
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Reject Ho
instructional implementation	Correlation Coefficient	0.921	0.293
	p-value	0.020	0.000
	Interpretation	Significant	Significant
	Decision	Reject Ho	Reject Ho
	Correlation Coefficient	0.092	0.274
	p-value	0.655	0.000
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Reject Ho

Relationship between the Level of Competencies of Mathematics Teachers as assessed by themselves and their students and Teachers IPCRF Rating

Based on the result in this study, it shows that there are no significant relationship between the level of competencies of mathematics teachers in terms of dedication to teaching, knowledge of subject matter, classroom organization and management, instructional organization and instructional implementation as assessed by themselves and their students and teachers' IPCRF rating. It implies that even if teachers are dedicated to teach, knowledgeable to the subject matter, classrooms are well – organized and the instructions are well – prepared and well – implemented, it does not necessarily lead to better IPCRF ratings. The interpretation that IPCRF ratings may not be solely related to certain teaching skills is consistent with existing research in the field. For example, a review by Hattie and Timperley (2017) found that teacher quality is a complex and multi-dimensional construct that involves different elements, such as classroom management, pedagogical content knowledge, and teacher-student relationships. Therefore, it is possible that factors beyond the ones assessed in the present study influence performance ratings.

Table 9. Relationship between the Level of Competencies of Mathematics Teachers as assessed by themselves and their students and Teachers IPCRF Rating

Competency Level of Mathematics Teachers		Teachers' IPCRF Rating	
		As Assessed by Teachers	As Assessed by Students
Dedication to Teaching	Correlation Coefficient	0.117	0.146
	p-value	0.569	0.477
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
Knowledge of Subject Matter	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
	Correlation Coefficient	0.267	0.001
	p-value	0.187	0.997
Classroom Organization and Management	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
	Correlation Coefficient	0.219	0.336
Instructional Organization	p-value	0.282	0.094
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
Instructional Implementation	Correlation Coefficient	0.323	0.068
	p-value	0.107	0.741
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho
	Correlation Coefficient	0.194	0.143
	p-value	0.342	0.486
	Interpretation	Not Significant	Not Significant
	Decision	Failed to Reject Ho	Failed to Reject Ho

Relationship between the Mathematics Performance of Students and their Teachers' IPCRF Rating

The correlation coefficient of 0.109 suggests that there is a weak positive relationship between the IPCRF rating of teachers and students' Mathematics performance. However, the p-value of .595 indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant. This means that there is no evidence to suggest that the IPCRF rating of teachers has a significant impact on mathematics performance. Therefore, the decision is not significant and we fail to reject the null hypothesis (Ho) and that there is no significant relationship between IPCRF ratings of teachers and students' mathematics performance. It implies that IPCRF ratings of teachers may not be a reliable predictor of academic performance in mathematics and that other factors, such as student ability, study habits, and classroom environment, may be more important in determining student achievement in this subject. Teacher competence is positively related to teaching quality, which in turn has an effect on student outcomes (Kunter, Klusmann, Baumert, Richter, Voss, & Hachfeld, 2013). Teacher competence, on the other hand, may serve as an important lever that can be used to improve the quality of teaching and student outcomes, for instance, in professional development programs (Kleickmann, Tröbs, Jönén, Vehmeyer, & Möler, 2016).

Table 10. Relationship between the Mathematics Performance of Students and their Teachers' IPCRF Rating

IPCRF Rating of Teachers		Mathematics Performance in Mathematics
Correlation Coefficient		0.109
p-value		.595
Interpretation		Not Significant
Decision		Failed to Reject Ho

Conclusions

The findings of this study suggested that students' mathematics performance was significantly affected by both their teachers' civil status and the level of training they received. These findings could have important implications for teacher training and professional development programs, as well as for school policies aimed at promoting equity and ensuring that all students have access to high-quality instruction. Similarly, those who have had access to higher levels of training and education may have had more opportunities to develop stronger mathematical skills and knowledge. However, the competency levels of teachers in terms of dedication to teaching, knowledge of the subject matter, classroom organization and management, instructional organization, and instructional implementation were found to be significantly related to students' mathematics performance as assessed by students themselves. These results have important implications for teacher training and development programs. Trainings should focus on developing these competencies as a way to enhance student outcomes. However, these competencies may not be strongly related to the IPCRF of teachers, but they were found to be significantly related to student mathematics performance. This highlights the importance of developing and improving these competencies as a way to ensure that students are receiving high-quality mathematics instruction.

Further, the demographic factors may not be reliable predictors of teacher effectiveness as measured by the IPCRF rating. This could have important implications for teacher evaluation and professional development programs. Additionally, it underscores the importance

of providing ongoing opportunities for professional development to all teachers, regardless of their demographic background.

It is recommended that the Education Program Supervisor in Mathematics and Department of Education identify the competencies of K–12 mathematics teachers that need improvement. This would help in developing in-service training and workshops to enhance the competence and performance of mathematics teachers. Additionally, mathematics teachers should upgrade themselves and strengthen the teaching strategies necessary to improve students' academic performance. This study would give insights to mathematics teachers to expand their teaching skills; thus, it is essential for them to focus on improving their instructional organization, classroom organization, knowledge of the subject matter, dedication to teaching, and instructional implementation so that positive learning outcomes will be attained.

Moreover, this study recommends that junior high school students use the findings to become aware of their Math performance, their strengths, and weaknesses. They should work on developing their problem areas to enhance their academic performance in Mathematics subject.

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